

DEWAN SIR MIRZA ISMAIL'S ACHIEVEMENTS TO MYSORE PRINCELY STATE: AN HISTORICAL ANALYSIS

Dr.B.R.Chandrashekharaiiah
HOD and Assistant Professor, Department of History
Sree Siddaganga College of Arts Science and Commerce, Tumkur

Abstract

The present study mainly aims to analyze the achievements of Dewan Sir Mirza Ismail in Mysore Princely State, he was born on 24 October 1883 in Bangalore into a Persian family, who fled Persia and took refuge under the wings of the Maharaja of Mysore. Sir Mirza Ismail joined government service as assistant superintendent of police after he graduated from Central College. In 1905, the Maharaja was appointed as his private secretary. In 1926, he took charge as Dewan of Mysore. There are important achievements such as industrial development, rural development, rural electrification, agricultural development, town planning, round table conferences, and the prime minister of Jaipur. This paper highlighted some important achievements of the Dewan period from Mysore Princely State. Also, it explained the role of Dewan and early life, personal life, and the rule of Dewan in both Mysore and Hyderabad states.

Keywords: Sir Mirza Ismail, Early Life, Dewan of Mysore, and Achievements.

INTRODUCTION

Sir Mirza Muhammad Ismail known as Amin-ul-Mulq was the Diwan of the Kingdoms of Mysore, Jaipur, and Hyderabad. He was an administrative period between 24th October 1883 and January 5th, 1959; was an Indian statesman who was the Diwan of the Kingdoms of Mysore, Jaipur, and Hyderabad. He also encouraged setting up many other industries such as Glass industry, Porcelain factory, Fertilizer industry at Belagola, Sugar factory at Mandya, Matchstick factory at Shivamogga and Iron and Steel factory at Bhadravathi. Many developments took place during Naalvadi Krishnaraja Wodeyar's rule. The term of Dewan is a Prime Minister. Sir Chetpat Pattabhirama Ramaswami Iyer, Diwan, Travancore considered him one of the cleverest men in India. Long-time friend Sir Chandrasekhara Venkata Raman said that Sir Mirza's accessibility and personal charm

coupled with his depth of knowledge and keen sense of human and cultural values made him a great and highly successful administrator. He focused on diversifying the industrial base and established several industries such as sugar factories in Shimoga, Khadi Production Centers in Badanval, and the Porcelain and Glass Factories in Bangalore.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

1. To study the role of Dewan Sir Mirza Ismail in Mysore princely state.
2. To review the important achievements of Dewan Mirza Ismail in the Princely State of Mysore.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This present article is mainly based on secondary information. It has been collected from various epigraphic and wikipedia, Gazetteer of Government of Karnataka, published and unpublished theses, refuted scholarly journals, etc. The article is limited and find out only up to Dewan Mirza Ismail and he was some important achievements of Mysore princely state.

EARLY LIFE JOURNEY OF DEWAN MIRZA ISMAIL

Mirza Ismail was born on 24th October 1883 in Bangalore into a Persian family, who fled Persia and took refuge under the wings of the Maharaja of Mysore. He was the grandson of Ali Asker. Krishnaraja Wodeyar-IV and he were classmates in college. After his graduation from Bangalore in 1904, he started off as an Asst. Superintendent of Police with the Government. After his early education at St Patrick and Wesleyan Schools in the city, he went to Royal School from 1901 along with Krishna Raja Wodeyar-IV. He joined government service as assistant superintendent of police after his graduation from Central college. In 1905, the Maharaja appointed as his private secretary. In 1926, he took charge as Dewan of Mysore. He went on to make a mark for 15 years on the strong foundation laid by his predecessor.

Personal Life

He was the grandfather Ali Askar was a Persian trader, who fled Iran and took refuge under the wings of the Maharaja of Mysore. He and his brother, Aga Abbas Ali,

prospered wildly under the patronage of the Maharaja. They trained the royal cavalry and supplied horses to the royal and army stables. Over time, Ali Askar evolved into a prominent builder and landowner in Bangalore and adjoining areas. He created the Ali Asker Waqf Estate which owns the land upon which the Windsor Manor hotel in Bangalore is built. Two roads in Bangalore have been named in honour of the two brothers, namely Ali Askar Road and Aga Abbas Ali Road. Mirza Ismail married Zeebunde Begum Shirazi in a match arranged by their parents in the usual Indian way. They had three children, a son who they named Humayun Mirza, and two daughters, Shah Taj Begum and Gauhar Taj Begum.

One of Mirza Ismail's cousins was Khaleel Shirazie, an affluent businessman whose business empire extended from Madras to Singapore and China. Two of Mirza Ismail's children (Humayun Mirza and Shah Taj Begum) were married to two of Khaleel Shirazie's children. Mirza Ismail's younger daughter, Gauhar Taj Begum, was given in marriage to Mirza Namazie's son, Mirza Ghulam Hussain Namazie, who was Director of M.A. Namazie Ltd. in Singapore, which is where he lived. M. M. Ispahani the founder of The House of Ispahani and M. M. Ispahani Limited one of Bangladesh most illustrious businessmen was another of Mirza Ismail's cousin.

Sir Mirza's grandson, Akbar Mirza Khaleeli (son of Shah Taj Begum) joined the Indian Foreign Service in 1959 and retired in 1994. At various times, he served as ambassador in Iran, Italy and Australia. Even after his retirement, he served as Advisor to the Indian government on Middle Eastern Affairs for many years. He was married to his cousin Shakereh née Namazie (daughter of Gauhar Taj begum), herself a granddaughter Mirza Ismail. The couple became the parents of four daughters but grew estranged. In 1991, Shakereh Khaleeli was murdered (sedated and buried alive) by a confidant who wanted to usurp her property, a large house with a vast garden at a very posh location in downtown Bangalore. A final verdict of life imprisonment was awarded to her murderer in 2008. They have four daughters: Zeebunde Khaleeli, Sabah Backhache, Rehane Yavar Dhala and Esmath Khaleeli. Agha Shahi and Agha Hilaly also inspired by Mirza Ismail, they chose to migrate to Pakistan during partition and became Foreign Secretaries of the Nation.

IMPORTANT ACHIEVEMENTS OF DEWAN MIRZA ISMAIL

DEWAN OF MYSORE STATE

He was first dewan of Mysore Princely State and ruler of Dewans in the state. He became the private secretary to the Maharajah, who had great faith in his administrative acumen and abilities to implement them. It was at this time the King urged Sir Mokshagundam Visvesvaraya to guide him. It is well documented that Sir Mokshagundam Visvesvaraya became Mirza Ismail's mentor. In 1926 on the recommendation of Vishvesvaraya the King supplemented Mirza Ismail by elevating him to the coveted position of the Diwan of Mysore. The Bangalore Town Hall was built by the King of Mysore, and designed by Mirza Ismail. In India, the first rural electrification scheme was also implemented by him.

The Nobel laureate Sir C.V. Raman paid eloquent tributes to Sir Mirza in the following words; For many years, in fair weather as well as in foul, Sir Mirza Ismail remained the truest of friends to me, ever ready to give support and advice. He leaves behind him a memory which will be treasured and cherished by all who have known him. He was an excellent administrator and set an inspiring instance to the officials by undertaking extensive tours and personally looking to the protests of the people. Over his fourteen years of service, Mysore State made substantial development in the field of industries, both in the private and public sectors. The sugar factory at Shimoga and the Khadi Production Centre at Badanval were the other industries that were set up during his time. A trade commissioner was also appointed in London.

Industries started during his period as diwan include Porcelain Factory and the Glass Factory all in Bangalore were established paper, cement, steel, fertilizers, sugar and electric bulbs. Vysya Bank, cement factory, the Chemical and Fertilizers factory and Sugar mills. In general, he did not exhibit major religious biases, though it is not clear why he was instrumental in setting up a mosque in Bangalore. In 1940, at the height of religious strife in India, he laid the foundation stone of the Jamia Masjid mosque, near City Market in Bangalore, very close to the town hall also built by him.

A main part of his administration was expended in suppressing many kinds of public disturbances. However, he had to do a great deal of tight-rope walking in the face of popular agitations conducted by the Congress Party. He had to maintain good relations with the top Indian National Congress leaders like Gandhi and Nehru on one hand and in alliance with Maharaja Krishnaraja Wodeyar IV, he did everything possible to suppress Congress movement in the State for fear of communal violence and unrest on the Garden City of India. It was this very fear which came to the fore over Sultanpet Ganapathi Disturbances in Bangalore in 1928 this upheaval created the long desired opportunity the Congress desired and they finally gained ground in the illusive state of Mysore also. Following the King Krishnaraja Wodeyar-IV death in 1940, he continued as the Diwan with king Jayachamaraja Wodeyar. However, he resigned in 1941 over differences.

DEWAN OF JAIPUR

He is one of the achievements of dewan of Jaipur. In 1941, he joined the Kingdom of Jaipur in Rajasthan as the Prime Minister. The chamber of commerce in Jaipur duly recorded the regime of Sir Mirza Ismail was the beginning of the Industrial era of Jaipur. Soon after his arrival in Jaipur, in 1942, he constituted a committee on Constitutional Reforms, these efforts considerably enhanced HH Maharaja Sawai Man Singh II's reputation and his Durbar in the Congress circles. The main thoroughfare of Jaipur has been named Mirza Ismail Road in his memory. Ghanshyam Das Birla was a close friend of Sir Mirza Ismail who used to fund the grand projects Mirza Ismail envisaged for Jaipur. When banks were permitted to open branches in Jaipur, United Commercial Bank, under chairmanship of GD Birla, was the first to be permitted to open a branch there in 1945. The National Ball-bearing company was established under guidance from Sir Mirza. In 1945, he presided the Indian Writers Council for the International PEN in Jaipur where Sarojini Naidu and Edward Morgan Forster were some of the attendants. Even after resigning as Prime Minister Sir Mirza Ismail remained advisor to the State and its affair pertaining to development. 1949 he was instrumental with the sanctioning of the building for the Jaipur Medical Association.

DIWAN OF HYDERABAD

The second achievement of dewan of Hyderabad. Muhammad Ali Jinnah had a fall out with Mirza Ismail when he refused to help build a Great Pakistan, this decision was made because Mirza Ismail objected to the Partition of India in entirety and there was nothing beyond India for him in 1945. So, it came as no surprise when Jinnah heard that Mirza Ismail was considering moving to Hyderabad, he opposed the decision openly. During 1946-47, He finally accepted and became Diwan of Hyderabad, also called Sadar-i-Azam (Prime Minister), during the difficult years of 1946–48 of the Princely State of Hyderabad, while Lt. General Mir Osman Ali Khan (r.1911–48).

Hyderabad was ruler of Sir Mirza Ismail put forth his best skills on the issue of accession of Hyderabad and negotiated a Standstill agreement with the Indian Government for a one-year period to resolve the issue of accession of Hyderabad province to the Indian government amicably. Pro-India leaders like Nawab Mehadi Nawaz Jung, Barrister Akbar Ali Khan, famous editor Sohaibulla Khan, Nawab Ali Yavar Jung and others supported the peace moves of Sir Mirza Ismail and tried to change the attitude of the Nizam from confrontation to coordination. With the assassination of Mohandas K. Gandhi, the Nizam became more set against acceding to India and took on a militant stand. As a result, Sir Mirza Ismail resigned from his post in disgust, which led to a very public and unpleasant interview by the Nizam. Soon after in 1948 as a result of insubordination the police launched Operation Polo and Hyderabad became part of the Indian Union in 1948.

BEAUTIFICATION

In this another achievement of beautification. He was good aesthetic and he was largest trait and responsible for the beatification of both Bangalore and Mysore states. Maharaja Krishna Raja Wodeyar took charge the state administration in 1902. In 1927, he completed his 25 years of rule despite various hurdles. He was ably assisted by Mirza and his team. They celebrated the silver jubilee of Maharaja's rule with several developmental projects in Bangalore and Mysore State. During his period to construct the eastern wing of Glass House at Lalbagh and to put up chandeliers namely lampposts in various spots of the city, indigenous materials from VISL Bhadravati were used. Transfer of a beautiful hexagonal stone structure from Dewan PN Krishna Murty's houses near Race Course to

Lalbagh West Gate, laying of silver jubilee park at Narashimha Raja road and several more such other works stand as a testimony to his efforts to beautify the capital. Some ovals with a small garden were also made in some parts of the city. The other one was in front of the City Market with a long lamp post of five dome lights and garden.

DIPLOMACY

Sir Mirza Ismail was a famous diplomat in the Mysore princely state. He was a harmonious relationship with the British and Indian National Congress. Talks with Mahatma in 1927. Persuaded Viceroy Irwin to reduce the annual tribute (34 lakhs to 24.5 lakhs). Attended the Round Table Conference in 1932.

HYDRO ELECTRIC PROJECTS

This is another achievement of the dewan period in the state. He was major strengthening of Hydro Electric Projects. Capacity of the power station of Shivanasamudra was increased. He was also started the Shimsha Power Station in 1940 and the Sharavti Project near Jogfalls in 1938 (it led to establish the Mahatma Gandhi Hydro Electric Station – 1948). Further worked on Rural Electrification started first time in India during 1940 and also it is benefited about 180 villages electrified.

OTHER ACHIEVEMENTS

Dewan Sir Mirza Ismail was another achievement of established the agriculture college at Hebbal with first steps to develop Sericulture sector. The other achievements like Chaluvamba Maternity Hospital at Mysore; Railway offices at Mysore; Radio Station at Mysore; Craft Institute at Bangalore; Mental Hospital at Bangalore; Narasimharaja Hospital at Kolar; and Mecgann hospital at Shivamogga. The freedom movement which had taken the country by storms after 1917 began to engulf the Mysore state during Mirza's period. There were disturbances like the Sultan pet Ganapati episode during the year 1928-29.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, Dewan Sir Mirza Ismail is one of the famous dewans of Mysore Princely State. He was also known as Statesman and both the former diwan of Mysore, Hyderabad. He was very biggest trait and responsible for the beatification of both Bangalore and Mysore. A fascinating story about him goes that he did not simply glance around to check if things were in good condition. He would lift the corner of a carpet to see if the floor had been swept. Mysore still proudly flaunts the label of the Garden City of India. This paper focused on another important achievements of agriculture college at Hebbal with first steps to develop Sericulture sector. The other achievements like Chaluvamba Maternity Hospital at Mysore; Railway offices at Mysore; Radio Station at Mysore; Craft Institute at Bangalore; Mental Hospital at Bangalore; Narasimharaja Hospital at Kolar; and Mecgann hospital at Shimogga. The freedom movement which had taken the country by storms after 1917 began to engulf the Mysore state during Mirza's period. He was succeeded by Dewan N. Madhav Rao. Jayachamaraja Wodeyar was the last Maharaja of Mysore. He was the adopted son of KRW IV. The last Dewan of Mysore was Arcot Ramaswamy Mudaliyar. The post of Dewan was abolished in 1949.

REFERENCES

- Akki, B. N. (2012). The Mysore Economic Conference: Its role in the Promotion of Industries in the Princely State of Mysore 1911-1932. *Pragmata: Journal of Human Sciences*, 1(1), 21-26.
- Manor, J. (1975). Princely Mysore before the Storm: The Statelevel Political System of India's Model State 1920—1936. *Modern Asian Studies*, 9(1), 31-58.
- Murthy, K. (2012). Economic Policy and Development of Princely Mysore: An Appraisal of Dewan Mirza Ismail's Role. *Board of Editors*, 241.
- Narayanrao, V.S. (V.S.N. henceforth) Sir Mirza Ismail (kan.) 1995, p.2.
- Sir Mirza M. Ismail; views and opinions on his retirement from the office of Dewan of Mysore, Bangalore City, Printed at the Bangalore Press, 1942.
- Department of Information (1952), Mysore on the march (24th October 1947-26th January 1950) a review of the activities of the several departments of government. Bangalore, Principal Information Officer to the Govt. of Mysore [1952], Mysore.
- Koppal, Basavaraj (2013). "Hyderabad Liberation – 10". Dharwad.com. Archived from the original on 29 July 2013.
- Rukshana, P. (1998). SirMirzain Hyderabad State. In *Studies on Dewan Sir Mirza Ismail: collection of seminar papers* (p. 60). The Mythic Society.
- Sreenivas Aingar, (Sreenivas Aingar henceforth), Amin-ul-Mulk Sir Mirza M.Ismail, 1944, p.8.
- Sugitha, S. (2014). Politics of dissent and development Mysore 1901 1909.
- Veerathappa, K. (1979, January). Dewan Mirza Ismail and Mysore Congress. In *Proceedings of the Indian History Congress* (Vol. 40, pp. 653-661). Indian History Congress.